

5. ISAF 2025

INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM
for AGRICULTURE AND FOOD

8-10 October 2025

Book of Abstracts

Organized by:

Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Food - Skopje,
Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje

Republic of North Macedonia
**Ministry of agriculture,
forestry and water economy**

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The Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Food-Skopje is organizing the **5th International Symposium for Agriculture and Food (ISAF-2025)**, which offers a possibility for presenting novel and fundamental advances in the field of sustainable agriculture and food production. ISAF 2025 will bring together and foster the communication among leading researchers, engineers and practitioners with an aim to share their scientific ideas and experiences with all actors in the agricultural sector. Since 2012, the International Symposium for Agriculture and Food is integrating the previous organized events: Faculty-Economy Meeting, Symposium of Viticulture and Wine Production, Symposium for Vegetable and Flower Production and International Conference of the Association of Agricultural Economists of the Republic of North Macedonia.

EVENTS WITHIN ISAF 2025

- 41st Faculty-Economy Meeting
- 14th International Conference of the Association of Agricultural Economists of the Republic of North Macedonia (AAEM)
- Meeting of the Association of Faculties of Agricultural Sciences of South Eastern Europe
- 10th Balkan Animal Sciences Conference BALNIMALCON 2025
- General Assembly of Agro-Well – Horizon Europe Project
- Beyond the leaf: Innovation, Research & Regulation - Philip Morris Panel Discussion
- Biobased Technologies for Climate-Resilient Farming: The DIVAGRI Project Approach
- AgriFood Business x EDIH: Innovate, Connect, Transform

SCIENTIFIC AREAS OF ISAF 2025

The topics of ISAF 2025 are divided into the following scientific sections:

- Animal Biotechnology & BALNIMALCON 2025
- Agricultural Economics
- Agricultural Machinery and Sustainable Agriculture
- Apiculture
- Phytomedicine - Plant Protection
- Food Quality and Safety
- Fruit Growing, Viticulture and Wine Production
- Vegetable, Flower and Decorative Plants Production
- Digital Agriculture & Natural Resources Management
- Field Crop Production
- Genetics, Breeding and Genetic Resources

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PLENARY SPEAKERS

Prof. Dr. Dragi Dimitrievski, Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Food-Skopje, North Macedonia

Title: From Support to Resurgence – A Vision for the Macedonian Agri-Food Sector

Prof. Dr. Dragi Dimitrievski is a full professor at the Institute of Agricultural Economics at the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Food-Skopje, University Ss. Cyril and Methodius in Skopje, and a former Vice-dean for sciences (2003–2005) and former Dean of the Faculty (2009–2017). His research interests and contributions include applied macro-economic analysis in the field of agriculture, with focus on agricultural and rural development policy. Dr. Dragi Dimitrievski is key national expert for agricultural policy and has been actively involved as researcher in different national and international projects related to agricultural and rural development policy analysis. For almost two decades, he is national expert within the Regional Rural Development Standing Working Group in South Eastern Europe (SWG). Dr. Dragi Dimitrievski is regularly being consulted on different important issues regarding the agricultural economics, so as a leader of various national projects, he contributed to development of significant number of strategic and legal documents regarding agricultural policy and rural development. His contribution is especially evident during the food crises due to the Covid-19 and the war in Ukraine, both as support to the policy makers, but also to media to update the public with reliable and thorough information regarding food security issues. All his knowledge and experience in this field he transfers to students through courses in Agricultural Policy that he lectures at all three study cycles, as well as in the course Human Resources Development on the undergraduate studies. Dr. Dragi Dimitrievski has published more than 100 articles in academic journals and international conference proceedings, as well as chapters in different monographs and two textbooks in the field.

PLENARY SPEAKERS

Prof. Dr. Cecilia Costa, CREA, Italy

Title: The most essential of all agricultural activities: apiculture

Dr. Cecilia Costa holds a degree in Agricultural Science and a PhD in Agricultural Biotechnologies. She is a Principal Researcher at CREA, the Italian Agricultural Research Council, where she has led research for over two decades on honey bee breeding and the biodiversity of *Apis mellifera*. Her work emphasizes disease resistance, genotype–environment interactions, and colony health and welfare. Dr. Costa is an active member of the COLOSS Association for the prevention of honey bee colony losses and currently coordinates an EU Horizon project. She has authored approximately 70 scientific publications and is a frequent invited lecturer at national and international apicultural and scientific events.

Prof. Dr. Hossein Azadi, Department of Geography, Ghent University, Belgium

Title: Tipping Points and Resilient Agriculture: How Climate-Smart Agriculture Can Support Small-Scale Farmers

Prof. Dr. Hossein Azadi obtained his first PhD in agricultural economics and the second in human geography. He is currently a professor at Ghent University in Belgium. He has published about 500 journal articles with +13000 citations and h-index of 60 underscoring him as top 3% global scientist ranked by AD Scientific index. His main focus is on land governance, the impacts of climate change on small-scale farmers, and agroecology. He is a member of the editorial boards in Land Use Policy, Land Degradation & Development, Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems, and Climatic Change. He also serves as a research project evaluator for several international councils and organizations.

PANEL DISCUSSIONS

1. The Role of Innovation and Technology in Climate Change Adaptation in Agriculture

Moderator: Prof. Dr. Vjekoslav Tanaskovikj

Prof. Dr. Zdenko Loncaric, Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences, Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek, Croatia

Prof. Dr. Hossein Azadi, Department of Geography, Ghent University, Belgium

Prof. Dr. Ordan Cukaliev, Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Food-Skopje, North Macedonia

Prof. Dr. Mirela Kajkut Zeljković, Institute of Genetic Resources of University of Banja Luka, Bosnia and Hercegovina

Mr. Boban Ilic, SWG

2. From Farm to Global Market: Rethinking Agri-Food Trade

Moderator: Neda Gruevska

Prof. Dr. Ruzica Loncaric, Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences, Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek, Croatia

Prof. Dr. Vlade Zaric, Faculty of Agriculture, University in Belgrade, Serbia

Prof. Dr. Bozidar Ivanov, Institute of Agricultural Economics, Sofia, Bulgaria

Dr. Ljupco Veleski, Vitaminka AD Prilep, North Macedonia

Sinisha Stefanovski, LK Raspberry DOOEL, North Macedonia

GENERAL PROGRAMME OF ISAF 2025

Date and Time	Programme	Hall
Day 1: 8 October 2025		
09.00–17.30	Registration of participants	Lobby
09.15–15.00	General Assembly of Agro-Well – Horizon Europe Project	Banket
16.00–17.30	Meeting of the Association of Faculties of Agricultural Sciences of Southeast Europe	Banket
18.00–19.00	Opening Ceremony	Biljana
19.00–19.30	Plenary Session 1	Biljana
19.30–21.30	Welcome Reception	Lobby
Day 2: 9 October 2025		
09.00–10.00	Plenary Session 2a & 2b	Biljana
10.00–10.30	Coffee Break	Lobby
	Parallel Sections 1	Biljana, Car Samoil, Kaneo, Ohrid, Labino, Banket
10.30–12.00	Beyond the leaf: Innovation, Research & Regulation - Philip Morris Panel Discussion	Car Samoil
12.00–12.30	Coffee Break	Lobby
	Parallel Sections 2	Biljana, Car Samoil, Kaneo, Ohrid, Labino, Banket
12.30–14.00	AgriFood Business x EDIH: Innovate, Connect, Transform	Green
	Biobased Technologies for Climate-Resilient Farming: The DIVAGRI Project Approach	Banket
14.00–15.00	Lunch	
15.00–16.00	Panel Discussion 1	Biljana
16.00–16.30	Coffee Break	Lobby
16.30–18.00	Parallel Sections 3	Biljana, Car Samoil, Kaneo, Ohrid, Labino, Banket
20.00	Gala Dinner	

Date and Time	Programme	Hall
Day 3: 10 October 2025		
09.00–10.00	Panel Discussion 2	Biljana
10.00–10.30	Coffee Break	Lobby
10.30–12.00	Parallel Sections 4	Biljana, Car Samoil, Kaneo, Ohrid, Labino, Banket
12.00–12.30	Coffee Break	Lobby
12.30–13.45	Parallel Sections 5	Biljana, Car Samoil, Kaneo, Ohrid, Labino, Banket
13.45–14.00	Closing Ceremony	Biljana
14.00–15.00	Lunch	
15.00–18.00	Excursion (optional)	
15.00	Departure of participants	

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Abstract Submissions

Poster Presentation

Topics: Genetics, Breeding and Genetic Resources

Keywords: genetic diversity, seed composition, NIRS analysis, bioactive compounds, breeding potential

EVALUATION OF OIL AND PROTEIN CONTENT VARIABILITY IN CAMELINA GENOTYPES

Ana Marjanović Jeromela¹, Nada Grahovac¹, Dragana Rajković¹, Sandra Cvejić¹, Ankica Kondić Špika¹, Federica Zanetti²

¹Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Serbia; ²Dept. of Agricultural and Food Sciences (DISTAL), Alma Mater Studiorum - University of Bologna, Italy; ana.jeromela@ifvcns.ns.ac.rs

Camelina sativa (L.) Crantz, a re-emerging oilseed crop of the Brassicaceae family, has attracted growing attention due to its valuable seed oil composition and high-quality meal. The oil is rich in essential fatty acids and potentially beneficial for human health, while the protein-rich meal has value for animal feed. This study assessed the oil and protein content variability in 20 camelina genotypes selected from diverse origins. A field trial was conducted at the experimental site of Rimski Šančevi, Serbia, and seed composition was analyzed using near-infrared reflectance spectroscopy (NIRS). Oil content ranged from 29.90% to 36.73% (mean 33.22%), while protein content ranged from 29.02% to 35.59% (mean 32.84%). Analysis of variance showed significant genotypic differences ($p < 0.001$), and cluster analysis grouped genotypes into three major clusters with one unclassified genotype. The results confirm the existence of substantial genetic variability, which can be exploited in breeding programs aiming to improve camelina seed composition. As a result of ongoing breeding activities at the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops (IFVCNS), two camelina cultivars have been developed and commercially released: NS Slatka and NS Zlatka. These findings support the potential of camelina as a source of health-promoting bioactive compounds and contribute to its development as a sustainable crop for food and feed applications.

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